

Quick Guide: Linking a GitHub Repository to Zenodo

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This guide walks you through linking a GitHub repository to Zenodo to obtain a citable DOI and *optionally* submitting it to a Zenodo community.

Part 1: Linking Your GitHub Repository to Zenodo

Step 1: Connect your GitHub account

Log in to zenodo.org using your GitHub account or **connect your GitHub account via your Zenodo profile settings** (*my preference as I already had an existing Zenodo!*). Once connected, click your profile drop-down in the top-right corner and select **GitHub**.

Note: I used ORCID to sign up to Zenodo in the first place as this also makes it easier to connect to your ORCID ID too.

Step 2: Sync your repositories

On the GitHub page within Zenodo, click the **Sync now** button (top right) each time you visit to refresh the list of available repositories. This ensures any newly created or made-public repositories appear. (It may take a few minutes to refresh/load if you've made recent changes on GitHub.)

Step 3: Enable a repository

Scroll down the page to see your repositories. Already-enabled repositories are shown at the top with their DOIs. To enable a new repository, find it in the list below and click the toggle switch.

Note: Repositories must be publicly visible on GitHub before they can be enabled in Zenodo. Private repositories are not supported.

Step 4: Initiate your first release

After enabling the repository, you will be taken to a page showing your releases. Click the green button to be taken to GitHub to create your first release.

Step 5: Create the GitHub release

On GitHub, fill in the release details:

- **Tag:** used for versioning. Use numeric names with a 'v' prefix, e.g. v1.0.0. Tagging suggestions appear in the right-hand sidebar when you're creating the release so if you're stuck, just consult those.
- **Release title:** often the name of your project or the associated paper title.

- **Release notes:** a brief description of the repository, like what you'd include in a README.

Once you're happy with the details, click **Publish release**.

← Releases

New release

Tag: v1.0.0 Target: main

Excellent! This tag will be created from the target when you publish this release.

Release title

transcriptomics of Adenomyosis lesions using Nanostring GeoMX

Release notes

Select a previous tag to create generated release notes

Previous tag: Auto Generate release notes

Write Preview H B I E < > @

bla bla bla

Markdown is supported Paste, drop, or click to add files

Attach binaries by dropping them here or selecting them.

Set as a pre-release
This release will be labeled as non-production ready

Publish release Save draft

Tagging suggestions
It's common practice to prefix your version names with the letter v. Some good tag names might be v1.0.0 or v2.3.4.

If the tag isn't meant for production use, add a pre-release version after the version name. Some good pre-release versions might be v0.2.0-alpha or v5.9-beta.3.

Semantic versioning
If you're new to releasing software, we highly recommend to [learn more about semantic versioning](#).

A newly published release will automatically be labeled as the latest release for this repository.

If 'Set as the latest release' is unchecked, the latest release will be determined by higher semantic version and creation date. [Learn more about release settings](#).

Step 6: Your published release and Zenodo record

After publishing, the release will appear on your GitHub repository's releases page.

Releases / paper-publication

AlphaFold reveals how pathogenic Leptospira use cross-kingdom thiol-disulphide exchange to evade the membrane attack complex

Latest

ejohnson93 released this Aug 19, 2025 - 1 commit to main since this release paper-publicat... 1e6fdc3

paper-publication

Update README.md

Assets 2

Source code (zip)	Aug 19, 2025
Source code (tar.gz)	Aug 19, 2025

Zenodo will automatically archive the repository and assign it a DOI. You can view and edit the resulting Zenodo record at any time. An example record is shown below, and live examples from the CBF can be found at:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/16903768>
- <https://zenodo.org/records/20347641>
- <https://zenodo.org/records/14905734>

Each subsequent release will also get it's own personal DOI, whilst still linking back to the overall record.

Importantly, Zenodo makes it very easy/straight forward to add the DOI straight to your GitHub README. 😊

If you click the below button on your side bar a list of options to embed the DOI in the README will appear.

DOI Badge

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.18962395

Markdown

```
[!DOI](https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.18962395.svg)(https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18962395)
```

reStructuredText

```
.. image:: https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.18962395.svg
   :target: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18962395
```

HTML

```
<a href="https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18962395"> Organization

University of Liverpool 

[New upload](#)

[Records](#) [Requests](#) [Members](#)



1 results found

Sort by Newest

August 19, 2025 (paper-publication)

Software

Open

### CBFLivUni/Leptospira-LIC13259-C8G: AlphaFold reveals how pathogenic *Leptospira* use cross-kingdom thiol-disulphide exchange to evade the membrane attack complex

Johnson, Emily Jane 

Code to reproduce work in paper titled 'AlphaFold reveals how pathogenic *Leptospira* use cross-kingdom thiol-disulphide exchange to evade the membrane attack complex '

Part of [Computational Biology Facility - University of Liverpool](#)

Uploaded on August 19, 2025

 6

## Tips and Notes

- Each time you publish a new GitHub release, Zenodo creates a new versioned DOI. A concept DOI that links all versions together is also created automatically.
- You can edit the metadata of your Zenodo record (title, authors, description, keywords, licence) after publication using the Edit button on the record page.
- If your repository is private when you attempt to enable it, it will not appear in the Zenodo list. Make it public on GitHub first, then sync again.
- Further guidance is available in the [Zenodo documentation](#).

## Contacts

- If you have any questions about the contents herein, please contact the author, Emily Johnson at: [emily.johnson@liverpool.ac.uk](mailto:emily.johnson@liverpool.ac.uk) / [ejohn10@liverpool.ac.uk](mailto:ejohn10@liverpool.ac.uk)
- For broader CBF enquiries please contact: [cbf@liverpool.ac.uk](mailto:cbf@liverpool.ac.uk) OR
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